

Toughness of Carbon Fiber/Epoxy Laminates Based on Intermediate Modulus Fibers

Janis Varna and Lars Berglund
Dept. of Materials and Production Engineering
Luleå University of Technology
S-951 87 Luleå, Sweden

Abstract

The transverse mechanical behaviour of two composites with the same matrix: an AS4/8552 carbon fiber/epoxy composite and an IM8/8552 intermediate modulus composite was studied in unidirectional and cross-ply laminates. The influence of the chosen fibers on failure strain and strength as well as on the multiple cracking in cross-ply laminates was analysed. The transverse cracking toughness was not affected by the different fibers.

Keywords: carbon fiber/epoxy composite, strength, failure strain, cross-ply laminates, multiple transverse cracking.

Introduction

The carbon fibers commonly used in composites have high tensile strength and low failure strains as compared with glass fibers. The introduction of composites with intermediate modulus carbon fibers in aerospace applications is intended for structures where large stresses as well as strains are allowed.

The question is, however, how these improved elastic and strength properties in the fiber (longitudinal) direction are matched in the transverse direction. This problem is significant since commercial structures consist of multidirectional laminates. Under external loading the stress state in each individual layer is very far from one-dimensional. The accumulation of different types of damage governed by the matrix and fiber/matrix interface start a long time before final fracture. These damages may also cause a decrease in the final failure strain of the laminate and thus reduce and/or question the advantages of intermediate modulus composites.

In laminated composites the first type of damage is often transverse cracking in the 90°-layers. The two scientific problems related to transverse cracking are the description of the multiple cracking process (the onset of cracking, crack density versus applied load) and the influence of transverse cracking on thermo-elastic properties of the laminate. The sequence of the transverse cracking is highly dependent on the transverse mechanical properties of the unidirectional layers. The constraint effect of adjacent layers and residual thermal strains in the laminate are two additional effects.

The elastic properties in the transverse direction depend on both matrix and fiber properties. Since carbon fibers have very high anisotropy of elastic properties and their transverse

properties are not well known, it is difficult to predict how the use of intermediate modulus carbon fibers will change the composite transverse modulus.

The transverse strength of unidirectional composites depends on matrix properties as well as on the strength of the fiber/matrix interface, fiber volume fraction etc. When "high strength" fiber composites based on either regular "high strength" (HS) or the new "intermediate modulus" (IM) carbon fiber have the same matrix and fiber volume fraction, the main parameter seems to be the interfacial strength.

The objective of the present paper is to analyze and compare the transverse mechanical behaviour (unidirectional and in cross-ply laminates) of two composites with the same matrix: an HS carbon fiber/epoxy composite AS4/8552 and an intermediate modulus composite IM8/8552. Composites with the same matrix were chosen in order to expose the role of the different fibers. The experimental results for unidirectional properties are presented. The results for cross-ply laminates include the crack density - applied load relationships and the influence of the transverse cracking on elastic properties of the laminate and the final laminate fracture.

Experimental procedure

Carbon fiber/epoxy AS4/8552 and intermediate modulus carbon fiber/epoxy IM8/8552 composite laminates (90° and [0/90]s) were made by SAAB Military Aircraft. The prepreg was supplied by Hercules and has a toughened epoxy matrix. The recommended cure cycle for this material involves 3 hours at 177 °C at a pressure of 6 bars.

Twelve test specimens from each laminate with 120 mm gauge length and 22 mm wide were cut from fabricated plates using a circular diamond saw. The specimen ends were reinforced by glass fiber/epoxy tabs bonded using FM R 73M OST adhesive film and cured for 2 hours at 125 °C. The edges of the tension specimens were sanded and polished using 1200 grit SiC for unidirectional transverse specimens and 4000 grit SiC for [0/90]s specimens to be observed in the optical microscope. Then the specimens were dried in an oven at 90 °C for 3 hours to remove excess water absorbed during polishing. Specimens were kept in a desiccator until testing.

The specimens were tensile tested at a cross-head speed of 1.5 mm/min using an Instron 1272 testing machine with a dynamic load cell of type 2513-504. Strain measurements in the specimen axis direction were performed by a SANDNER- extensometer of type ExA10 - 2,5 with a gauge length of 50 mm. Strain gauges were used for transverse strains.

The registration of transverse cracking events in cross-ply laminates was partly performed using acoustic emission equipment. However, the acoustic signals generated during crack formation were very weak and quantitative analysis was possible just for AS4/8552 [0/90]s laminates. Optical observations of the specimen edges were therefore performed during the tests.

The data acquisition software package STATUS with PC-30 data acquisition board was used for data collection and analysis.

Transverse specimens were loaded in one step until final failure. Stress-strain curves were recorded. Longitudinal unidirectional specimens were loaded, unloaded and reloaded several times in order to obtain longitudinal strain, transverse strain and applied longitudinal stress relationships. Some longitudinal fracture data were also collected.

Cross-ply specimens were stepwise loaded, unloaded, taken out of the testing machine and observed in the microscope. Then followed the next step of loading etc. Longitudinal and transverse strains as well as applied stress were recorded during the test.

Results and discussion

Test results for unidirectional specimens (90° and 0°) are presented in Table I (average values and standard deviations (in parentheses)). Note, that the AS4/8552 ply is thicker than the IM8/8552 ply. Stress- strain relationships in transverse loading were for both materials straight lines until failure. The transverse failure strain of both materials is rather high, 0.7%. The transverse failure strain of T300/5208 based on a brittle epoxy matrix is about 0.38% [1]. The increased failure strain for AS4/8552 is likely to be due to the increased toughness of 8552 matrix. The transverse strength of IM8/8552 unidirectional specimens is about 10% lower than that of AS4/8552 specimens. The reason is the lower transverse modulus of IM8/8552 (also about 10 %).

The main reason for 0°-tests was to obtain elastic properties for the analysis of cross-ply laminates. The longitudinal stiffness of both materials showed stiffening at higher loads. The average moduli measured in the strain range between 0.1% to 0.3 % are presented in Table I. In the applied strain region 1% to 1.3% the tangential modulus of AS4/8552 was 16% higher and for IM8/8552 18% higher than the values in Table I. The longitudinal secant modulus in the full range was 7% and 9% higher, respectively.

The major Poisson's ratio ν_{LT} of IM8/8552 is slightly larger than that of AS4/8552. The results in Table I are obtained from the transverse strain - longitudinal strain relationships in the strain region 0.1% to 0.3%. It is remarkable that this relationship is nonlinear at higher strains : the increase of transverse strain becomes smaller at the same increase of longitudinal strain. Therefore the tangential value of the Poisson's ratio in the strain region 1% to 1.3 % is approximately 20% lower for AS4/8552 and 15% lower for IM8/8552 composite. The secant value of the Poisson's ratio in the whole strain region is 10% lower than in Table I for AS4/8552 and 5% lower for IM8/8552 . Only some longitudinal specimens were loaded until fracture, since that was not the objective of this study. These uncomplete data indicate that the longitudinal fracture strain of IM8/8552 specimens is just slightly higher than for AS4/8552 specimens. The longitudinal strength of IM8/8552 is higher and it is related to the higher longitudinal modulus and strength of intermediate modulus fibers.

The transverse cracking data for [0/90]_s laminates are presented in Fig.1 and Fig. 2. As a result of the mismatch in thermal expansion coefficients in fiber direction and transverse direction we have residual thermal tensile strains and stresses in the 90°-layer of the laminate. The value of thermal strains is about 0.3 % to 0.4% [2,3]. For this reason we could expect that the onset of transverse cracking in cross-ply laminates would start at significantly lower mechanical strains than the transverse failure strain of unidirectional laminates (see Table I). However, the test data show that the transverse cracking starts at about 0.6% mechanical strain in AS4/8552 cross-ply laminates and at 0.7% strain in IM8/8552 laminates. The reason for this phenomenon is known [2,4] and is called the constraint effect of the 0°-layers on the crack propagation in the 90°-layers. The transverse cracking strain in the IM8/8552 cross-ply laminate is higher for two reasons. The main reason is geometrical - the thickness of the 90°-layer in IM8/8552 laminate is smaller than in the AS4/8552 laminate and it is known that for thinner 90°-layers the constraint effect is stronger. The second reason is minor - the 0°-layers in the IM8/8552 cross-ply are stiffer than in the AS4/8552 laminate and that means a slightly higher constraining effect.

The multiple cracking process is slightly different in the two inspected cross-ply laminates. In the beginning phase the transverse cracking in AS4/8552 starts at lower strains and the number of transverse cracks increases faster. Later the cracking rate is reduced because of crack interaction. Since the 90°-layer of AS4/8552 is thicker, the interaction of transverse cracks in this material starts at lower crack densities. From this moment the increase of the crack density is faster in the IM8/8552 cross-ply laminate and at about 1.1% strain, it reaches the same value as AS4/8552. Since AS4/8552 laminates fail at $\approx 1.25\%$ strain and the IM8/8552 laminates at $\approx 1.35\%$ the final crack densities are difficult to compare. The crack density in the IM8/8552 cross-ply laminates continues to increase as fast as before until final failure takes place.

The observations of reduction in thermo-elastic properties during multiple cracking in carbon fiber/epoxy cross-ply laminates were difficult to interpret. The high stiffness of the 0°-layer as compared with the 90°-layer caused the stiffness reduction to be very small and comparable with the data scatter. The stiffening effect in the 0°-layers at higher loads is larger than the stiffness reduction caused by cracking. In the high strain region we therefore observe an increase of stiffness instead of a reduction. For this reason it is very important to perform stiffness measurements in the same strain region. Because of the difficulties described above it was decided to relate transverse cracking to the change in Poisson's ratio [5].

The transverse strain divided by the longitudinal strain curve is also quite nonlinear for cross-ply laminates of the inspected materials. This complicates the definition and calculation of the Poisson's ratio (Poisson's ratio is significantly higher in the low strain region). It was observed that the transverse cracking has a small influence on the Poisson's ratio when the ratio measurements are performed in the low strain region. If we choose a region of larger strains for the calculation of the secant Poisson's ratio, then the same changes in crack density cause much larger relative changes in Poisson's ratio. Because of these difficulties, the quantitative analysis of the influence of the transverse cracking on elastic properties still needs improvements and is not completed.

Conclusions

1. Elastic properties of two composite materials based on the same epoxy system - carbon fiber/epoxy AS4/8552 and intermediate modulus IM8/8552 - were examined in tests and analyzed. IM8/8552 had lower transverse modulus than AS4/8552 due to lower transverse modulus of the fiber. The materials both had unusually high transverse failure strains, 0.7%. The different fibers had no effect on this value.

2. The transverse cracking process in [0/90]_s cross-ply laminates was experimentally studied. The differences in the behaviour between the two materials are qualitatively explained by the differences in the main parameters controlling the constraint effect (90°-layer thickness and 0°-layer stiffness). The transverse cracking toughness was similar for laminates based on intermediate modulus fibers and for laminates with conventional fibers.

References

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Table I Properties of unidirectional AS4/8552 and IM8/8552 composites

Laminate	IM8/8552					AS4/8552				
	h(mm)	Strain at failure $\epsilon_u(\%)$	Strength $\sigma_u(\%)$	Modulus E(GPa)	Poisson's ratio ν_{LT}	h(mm)	Strain at failure $\epsilon_u(\%)$	Strength $\sigma_u(\%)$	Modulus E(GPa)	Poisson's ratio ν_{LT}
90 ₈	0.73 (0.02)	0.70 (0.09)	59.1 (6.0)	8.3 (0.4)	-	1.05 (0.02)	0.72 (0.06)	67.3 (5.0)	9.3 (2.0)	--
0 ₈	0.74 (0.04)	1.35	2500	167.6 (3.2)	0.34 (0.02)	1.02 (0.02)	1.30	1900	137.0 (4.0)	0.31 (0.03)

Fig.1. Experimental data for the crack density as a function of the applied mechanical strain in [0/90]s laminates.

Fig.2. Experimental data for the crack density as a function of the applied stress in [0/90]s laminates.